

A new Load Balance Methodology for Container Loading Problem in Road Transportation

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Abstract

The load balance aspect of the Container Loading Problem (CLP) has been handled in a simplified way in the literature. Either load balance has been treated as a soft constraint or the geometrical centre of the container has been assumed to be the ideal location for the centre of gravity of the cargo, or both, which does not meet regulatory directives and transportation legislation. In this paper we treat load balance as a hard constraint and adopt vehicle specific diagrams that define the feasibility domain for the location of the centre of gravity of the cargo, according to the vehicle specific technical characteristics, thus fulfilling and complying with real-world regulations and legislation. We propose a multi-population biased random-key genetic algorithm (BRKGA), with a new fitness function that takes static stability and load balance into account. Extensive computational experiments were performed with different variants of the proposed approach. Also solutions taken from the literature were evaluated in terms of load balance. The computational results show that it is possible to obtain stable and load balanced solutions without compromising the performance in terms of container volume utilization, and demonstrate also the advantage in incorporating load balance in the packing generation algorithm.

Keywords: Transportation in truck; container loading; weight; load balance; stability

1. Introduction

The container loading problem (CLP) is a real-world driven combinatorial optimization problem, of a strong impact on the economy, on the environment and on safety, which belongs to the class of Cutting & Packing (C&P) problems. In the literature the CLP is usually described as the packing of a set of boxes into a container, so that those boxes do not overlap and lie entirely inside the container, while maximizing the container space

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utilization. The problem has been addressed in the literature, focusing on the optimization of the spatial arrangement of the cargo inside cargo transport units (e.g. shipping containers, trucks, semi-trailers). However, the approaches to the CLP fail to yield solutions usable by practitioners, owing mainly to the excessive simplification of relevant practical constraints. The lack of a realistic representation of practical constraints has already been pointed out by Bortfeldt & Wäscher (2013), who made a state-of-the-art review work on constraints in CLP. From the exhaustive analysis of the literature on CLP published between 1980 and 2011 the authors concluded that even though the orientation and stability constraints are frequently considered, other constraints, such as weight distribution or weight limit, are less often taken into account.

In this paper we present a new approach to the CLP, in which a container is to be filled with a selection of boxes from an available set so that the volume utilization of the container is maximized, subject to load balance, weight limit and stability constraints. The arrangement of the boxes in the container must be orthogonal, and the boxes are not to overlap and must lie entirely within the container.

Static stability relates to the effect of the gravity force on the cargo arrangement inside the container. The cargo weight limit defines the maximum weight that can be loaded inside a container. Load balance relates to the location of the centre of gravity (CG) of the cargo and affects the manoeuvrability of the handling equipment as well as the behaviour of the transportation vehicle. The last two and usually result from regulatory and technical requirements.

In the Bortfeldt & Wäscher (2013) review of practical constraints in the CLP literature, using the work of Bischoff *et al.* (1995) as a starting point, a classification for CLP practical constraints was proposed. The authors distinguish between container-related constraints, box-related constraints, cargo-related constraints, positioning constraints and load-related constraints.

This classification translates the way how the practical constraints have been addressed in the literature and it does so remarkably well. However, it does not provide a general structure that allows for the establishment of a relation between constraints. For example, the weight distribution (a container-related constraint), is related to cargo stability (a cargo-related constraint), during transportation and yet they do not belong to the same category. Furthermore constraints of a different nature are also included in the same category. One example is the weight distribution constraint where weight distribution and load balance constraints are considered to be the same. The first concerns how the weight of the cargo is distributed on the base of the container so as not to exceed the maximum floor load, and is therefore related to the structural resistance of the container, whereas the latter relates to the location of the centre of gravity of the cargo and consequently concerns the interaction of the container with interacting elements such as trucks or cranes.

A new classification structure providing a base that relates the practical constraints was deemed necessary. Hence, the constraints identified in the literature were classified into two main types: safety and logistics constraints. Safety constraints relate to the integrity of the cargo and transport unit, as well as to the safety of workers and external parties during loading, handling and transportation operations. Logistics constraints address operational

decisions unrelated to the physical properties of the cargo and transport unit. Table 1 presents the practical constraints according to Bortfeldt & Wäscher (2013) organised in conformity with the classification proposed here.

Table 1: Practical constraints classification.

Safety constraints	Logistics constraints
weight limit	loading priorities
weight distribution	complete shipments
orientation	allocation
stacking	complexity
positioning (physical)	positioning (customer)
stability	

Safety constraints are strongly interrelated. The physical properties of the container and boxes influence how they sustain all the stress they are subjected to during handling and transportation. This paper will focus on the safety constraints by explicitly considering orientation, stability of the cargo, weight limit and load balance.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. In section 2 we describe in detail the CLP addressed in the paper. In section 3, we examine how stability, weight limit and load balance constraints have been dealt with in the literature.

In Section 4, Load Distribution Diagrams are presented together with the main concepts involved.

The complete solution method, comprehending a BRKGA algorithm and a Balance Recovery Algorithm that ensures stable and load balanced solutions, is presented in Section 5. In Section 6 the computational experiments conducted with the proposed algorithm are presented, together with an analysis of the results obtained and their comparison with others published in the literature. Finally, a summary of the approach and final conclusions are presented in Section 7.

2. Problem definition

The CLP addressed in this work can be stated as follows: A given set of small items of parallelepiped shape $k(k = 1, \dots, K)$, known as box types $B = b_1, b_2, \dots, b_K$, each box type in quantity n_k , assumed to be a rigid body with the centre of gravity located at its geometric centre, and characterized by its depth (d_k), width (w_k), height (h_k) and weight (p_k) is to be loaded orthogonally into a large object of parallelepiped shape, designated as container C , characterized by its depth (D), width (W) and height, (H), to be transported by a vehicle. The objective of the loading process is to achieve a maximum utilization of the volume of the container, while meeting the following constraints:

- the boxes must no overlap each other;
- all boxes must lie entirely within the container;
- each box can only be loaded through the container entrance;

- each box must be placed in accordance with one of its possible orientations;
- each box is to maintain its loading position undisturbed during cargo loading: if the partial loads obtained during the loading operations are statically stable, then also the full load will be statically stable (static stability constraint);
- the total weight loaded into the container is not to exceed its maximum permissible weight (weight limit constraint);
- the distribution of the weight of the cargo arrangement between the vehicle axles must be such that the limits determined by regulatory and technical requirements are not exceeded (load balance constraint).

The solution to the problem should provide the set of boxes to be loaded, the loading sequence of the boxes, and the location of each box inside the container.

According to the typology proposed by Wäscher *et al.* (2007) for C&P problems, the addressed CLP can be characterised as a 3-Dimensional Single Large Object Placement Problem (3D-SLOP) or a 3-Dimensional Single Knapsack Problem (3D-SKP), with additional constraints: cargo static stability, cargo weight limit and load balance constraints.

Load balance in road transport

Load balance in road transport concerns the distribution of the weight of the loaded vehicle among its axles. The vehicle, either a truck, a trailer, or a semi-trailer, requires a proper distribution of the weight between the axles to assure the transportation in safe conditions. The values that an axle can withstand are determined by both regulatory and technical requirements, and are specific to each vehicle.

The distribution of the weight of the loaded vehicle between the axles is strongly influenced by the weight and the position of the centre of gravity of the loaded cargo. Therefore each vehicle has specific diagrams that show the admissible cargo weight as a function of the position of the centre of gravity of the cargo, so that regulatory and technical requirements are fulfilled. Of the three dimensions of the centre of gravity, it is the longitudinal one that is taken into consideration to determine the distribution of the cargo weight between the vehicle axles. The transversal and vertical dimensions of the cargo centre of gravity only influence the lateral distribution of the weight.

One of the main tools used to assess the maximum permissible load weight on trucks and trailers is the load distribution diagram (LDD). The LDD is a two-dimensional plot that shows the maximum admissible load of a vehicle as a function of the longitudinal or transversal position of its centre of gravity, thus defining the area where the location of the cargo CG is acceptable. Figure 1a presents an example of the longitudinal LDD of a truck with three axles, loaded with three boxes, each one with a weight of 5 tnf (1 ton-force (tnf) = 8896.44 Newton (N)), and with the CG of the cargo located directly over the longitudinal geometric centre of the loading unit. Since the weight of the loaded cargo is less than the maximum possible value for this specific position of the cargo CG, the loading arrangement is admissible. If we remove one of the boxes from the container (Fig 1b), even though the

total loaded weight decreases from 15 to 10 tnf, owing to the shift of the cargo CG, the LDD shows that the loaded weight now exceeds the maximum admissible value for the shifted position of the cargo CG, wherefore this arrangement is not acceptable.

Figure 1

It can also be observed that the theoretical maximum vehicle load is only feasible within narrow boundaries in the vicinity of the geometric centre of the container (2,8-2,9 m measured from the back of the container, in this example) and that the geometric centre of the container does not necessarily lie within these boundaries. Therefore, the maximum weight that can be loaded into the container depends on the position of CG of the cargo arrangement and on the characteristics of the vehicle.

3. Literature Review

The container weight limit constraint represents the maximum weight that can be loaded inside a container. Typically, it is considered as a hard constraint and — in the case of cargo with a high volumetric mass density — the weight limit becomes, rather than container volume, the main constraint of the CLP.

The recent state of the art review of constraints in container loading by Bortfeldt & Wäscher (2013) refers that the weight limit constraint is considered in 14% of the papers on container loading, such as e.g., Gehring & Bortfeldt (1997), Liu & Hsiao (1997), Terno *et al.* (2000), Iori & Martello (2010), Chan *et al.* (2006), Egeblad *et al.* (2010) and Wang *et al.* (2010).

In mathematical formulations, the weight limit constraint is usually considered as a linear knapsack constraint, which ensures that the total weight of the cargo loaded is no higher than the weight limit imposed by the container. Regarding heuristic approaches, the weight limit of the cargo is easily validated by means of a straightforward procedure.

In recent works, Lim *et al.* (2013), Alonso *et al.* (2017) and Alonso *et al.* (2016), besides the total gross weight limit of the loading in a truck, algorithms are proposed that take into account the maximum weight that the axles of the vehicles can sustain. The inclusion of these limitations is of the utmost importance to the safety of the vehicle and is an important step towards real-world needs.

Load balance is an important constraint intrinsically related to the centre of gravity of the cargo loaded which, irrespectively of the various ways how it has been treated in the literature, has always been regarded as a soft constraint. Furthermore, some works consider only the longitudinal load balance (Chen *et al.* , 1995; Lim *et al.* , 2013), while others consider both the longitudinal and the transversal load balance (Haessler & Brian Talbot, 1990; Gehring *et al.* , 1990; Davies & Bischoff, 1999; Bortfeldt & Gehring, 2001; Techanitisawad & Tangwiwatwong, 2004; Moon & Nguyen, 2014), and some research takes all three dimensions in consideration: longitudinal, transversal and vertical load balance (Fasano, 2004; Egeblad & Pisinger, 2009; Liu *et al.* , 2011; Baldi *et al.* , 2012; Costa & Captivo, 2016; Alonso *et al.* , 2016).

The geometric midpoint of the container has been considered in the literature as the desirable location for the centre of gravity of the cargo. Different metrics have been used to classify the load balance of a packing scheme. Some approaches attempt to place the centre of gravity of the cargo as close as possible to the geometric centre of the container during the construction of the CLP solution. Examples of this strategy can be found in Eley (2002) and Alonso *et al.* (2016). A different procedure consists in defining a feasibility domain for the centre of gravity of the cargo. In Baldi *et al.* (2012) the centre of gravity of the cargo is to be located within $[\frac{L}{4}; \frac{3L}{4}]$ of the length, $[\frac{W}{4}; \frac{3W}{4}]$ of the width and $[0; \frac{H}{2}]$ of the height of the container, and in Moon & Nguyen (2014) a deviation of 5% in length and width is allowed. Some works mention that a tolerable distance to the geometric centre of the container can be accepted, although no values are given. This is the case of Gehring *et al.* (1990); Chen *et al.* (1995); Techanitisawad & Tangwiwatwong (2004) and Fasano (2004).

Whereas the aforementioned approaches take load balance into consideration during the solution construction process, other algorithms only address the load balance issue once the construction of a solution that maximises the volume occupation of the container is complete. Upon solution construction, a post-processing algorithm is run to improve load balance. In what concerns post-processing, the most common practices in the literature are the division of the container into disjunctive sections and the consideration of blocks during the development of the loading process. Once a complete solution has been created, the sections or blocks are interchanged or rotated in order to obtain a better load balance. This procedure can be found in Gehring *et al.* (1990); Gehring & Bortfeldt (1997); Davies & Bischoff (1999); Bortfeldt & Gehring (2001) and Eley (2002). In Baldi *et al.* (2012) the post-processing algorithm consists in moving items in a direction that produces a displacement of the centre of gravity of the load towards the desired domain, but the procedure considers neither box removal nor box addition and offers no guarantee that a load balanced solution is obtained in the end.

The load balance during the solution construction is considered in Haessler & Brian Talbot (1990) by alternating the packing of heavy and light stacks in the container. Costa & Captivo (2016) adopts a different strategy, namely the ordering of the corners of the container, with a box with the appropriate weight being selected for the specific corner. Aiming at keeping the centre of gravity of the cargo near the centre of the truck, Alonso *et al.* (2016) divides the truck into two sections: front and rear. Starting from the centre, the packing of the pallets is performed alternately in each section. In Wodziak & Fadel

(1994) a genetic algorithm for container loading is developed with a penalty associated with the deviation of the centre of gravity of the cargo from its desirable location. Although the previously adopted strategies consider load balancing during the solution construction, there is no guarantee that the final solution obtained is actually load balanced, with the genetic algorithm of Moon & Nguyen (2014) being the only exception, by accepting individuals in the population only if the centre of gravity of the cargo lies within its acceptable domain range.

In Trivella & Pisinger (2016) the load balance is considered in the multi-dimensional bin packing problem. The main goal is to minimize the number of used bins while the average center of mass of the cargo should be as close as possible to the geometric center of the container. A mixed-integer linear programming model is proposed and the problem has been solved by a multi-level local search heuristic that uses graph representation of feasible packings and dynamical search techniques for the recombination of n-tuples of weekly balanced bins.

In table 2 a summary of the container loading literature considering load balance is presented. The columns “CG” (2-4) present the axes directions analysed for load balance, the columns “Metrics for balance” (5-6) divide the papers into those that consider a feasible domain for the desired centre of gravity and those that try to minimize the distance to the desired centre of gravity, the “Phase” columns (7-8) represent the strategy adopted for the development of a load balanced solution, distinguishing between post-processing and the pursuit of load balance during the solution construction. If the paper presents computational results for load balance a “yes” is inserted in the column “Results”, otherwise a “no”. Column “Instances” presents the name of the problem instances used for testing the algorithms in the respective papers, the column “Weight limit” presents the values adopted for this parameter, whenever available and, finally, column “Item weight generation” presents the ranges used for the generation of the weight of the boxes.

Table 2: Load balance consideration in the literature

Publication	CG			Metrics for load balance		Phase		Results	Instances	Weight limit	Item weight generation
	x	y	z	Feasible Domain	Minimal Distance	Post processing	During construction				
Gehring <i>et al.</i> (1990)				x				No	Example		No
Haessler & Brian Talbot (1990)	x	x			x		x	No	Example		No
Wodziak & Fadel (1994)	x	x			x		x	No	Example		No
Chen <i>et al.</i> (1995)		x		x			x	No	Example		-
Gehring & Bortfeldt (1997)	x	x			Mean 10% in L and W	x		Yes	GB1-GB6	10 ton	U[90% mean box weight; 110% mean box weight]
Davies & Bischoff (1999)	x	x			Mean 6% in L, between 5 and 8% in W	x		Yes	BR	No info	U[50;5000], U[10;50] and U[960;100] kg/m^3
Bortfeldt & Gehring (2001)	x	x			$\leq 1\%$ in L and W	x		Yes	BR	No info	No info
Eley (2002)		x			$\leq 1cm$ in L	x		Yes	BR	No info	U[5000;50000], U[5000;100000], U[5000;250000] and U[5000;500000] kg/m^3
∞ Techanitisawad & Tangwiwatwong (2004)	x	x	x			x		No	Exp	[300;600] kg/m^3	U[1;50], U[51;100], U[101;150], U[151;200], U[201; 250], U[251;300], U[301;350], U[351;400], U[401;450], U[451;500] kg/m^3
Fasano (2004)	x	x	x	x		-	-	No	-	No info	No info
Egeblad (2009)	x	x	x		Euclidean distance ≤ 7	x		Yes	EP	-	-
Liu <i>et al.</i> (2011)	x	x	x		$< 50\%$ in L, W and H	x		Yes	Real	23,78 ton	No info
Baldi <i>et al.</i> (2012)	x	x	x		$[\frac{L}{4}; \frac{3L}{4}]$, $[\frac{W}{4}; \frac{3W}{4}]$, $[0; \frac{H}{2}]$	x		Yes	EP	No info	U[70;100], U[10;1000]
Lim <i>et al.</i> (2013)		x			$\leq 5 cm$	x		Yes	WL	21,64 ton	box density $\geq 110\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}$, box density $\in [100\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}; 110\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}]$, box density $\in [90\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}; 100\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}]$, box density $\leq 90\% \frac{C_w}{C_v}$
Moon & Nguyen (2014)	x	x		5% in L and W			x	Yes	BR	No info	U[77;769], U[47;933], U[19;798] kg
Costa & Captivo (2016)	x	x	x		$\leq 1\%$		x	Yes	Real	24 ton	No info
Alonso <i>et al.</i> (2016)	x	x	x		x		x	No	Real	No info	-
Trivella & Pisinger (2016)	x	x	x		x		x	Yes	Generated	No info	box density: 1; U[1;2]; U[1;6]

4. Load distribution diagrams

The section explains how to create a load distribution diagram (LDD) and the main concepts involved. To calculate an LDD, the geometry of the vehicle, the minimum and maximum admissible axle loads, the distribution of the tare weight by the different axles and the maximum admissible payload are required data (EC, 2014).

The calculation of the LDD is based on the static analysis of the external forces acting on a vehicle and makes direct use of static force equilibrium equations applied to rigid bodies (1), where \vec{F} represents the external forces applied to a rigid body, \vec{r} represents the vector from a given point O to the line of action of force \vec{F} and \vec{M}_O represents the moment of a force. The first equation guarantees translational equilibrium and the second guarantees rotational equilibrium (Hibbeler, 2010).

$$\begin{cases} \sum \vec{F} = \vec{0} \\ \sum \vec{M}_O = \sum (\vec{r} \cdot \vec{F}) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

4.1. Longitudinal load distribution diagrams

For the longitudinal LDD, the real vehicle is represented using a single track model, which assumes that:

- The vehicle is longitudinally symmetrical;
- The vehicle's mass is represented as a single mass concentrated at its CG;
- The tires on each axle are represented as a single tire on each axle;
- The tire contact point, i.e., the point where the tire forces are assumed to act upon, lies on the centre line of its axle.

The model of a symmetric n -axle vehicle is therefore equivalent to a rigid beam having n supports. However, if a vehicle has more than two axles ($n > 2$), the system is hyperstatic (an equation system where the number of unknowns is greater than the static equilibrium equations), and the axle loads cannot be determined by static equilibrium equations.

This poses a problem for the majority of the heavy commercial vehicles that have more than two axles. To simplify calculations, theoretical front-axle and rear-axle centre lines are used. These centre lines group several axles at one single point. When there is only one axle at the front or rear, the theoretical centre line coincides with the axle centre line. In a semi-trailer the front axle centre line is the "fifth wheel coupling" centre line. In practice, these data are usually not made available by the vehicle manufacturer and must be determined using the permissible load on each axle or group of axles and the wheelbase distance between each two consecutive axles of the vehicle to calculate the resultant permissible load and its location (MAN, 2016).

When addressing the permissible axle load, a distinction must be made between the technical and the regulatory admissible axle loads. The first concerns the characteristics,

condition and design of the axle, the latter relates to the laws that regulate the maximum authorised dimensions and weights for road vehicles. These values are specific to each country, and in the EU this issue is regulated by the Council Directive 96/53/EC of 25 July 1996 and the Directive (EU) 2015/719.

For example, the configuration of a 3-axle truck (Fig. 2), with a double rear axle with a spacing of 1.35 m, a permissible axle load on each rear axle of 9.5 tnf, and a wheelbase (WB) of 4.75 m corresponds to a theoretical centre line with an empty weight of 19 tnf and a theoretical wheelbase (TWB) of 5.425 m.

The vehicle data required for the calculation of the LDD are:

- U – Weight of unladen vehicle [tnf]
- FU – Weight of unladen vehicle transferred to the front axle [tnf]
- RU – Weight of unladen vehicle transferred to the rear axle [tnf]
- FTC – Theoretical front-axle centre line [m]
- RTC – Theoretical rear-axle centre line [m]
- TWB – Theoretical wheelbase – distance between front and rear theoretical load centres [m]
- D – horizontal distance between the theoretical front-axle centre line and the back of the cargo container [m]
- Cg – the centre of gravity of the unladen vehicle
- Hu – horizontal distance between the theoretical front-axle centre line and the centre of gravity [m]

Figure 2: Truck with three axles.

The limits of the LDD are hence determined in accordance with the regulatory and technical boundary conditions specified on the German standard VDI 2700 Part 4 (VDI, 2012), the EU Council Directive 96/53/EC of 25 July 1996 and Directive (EU) 2015/719, and should observe:

- The maximum permissible:
 - (a) front axle load;
 - (b) rear axle load;
 - (c) gross vehicle weight.
- The minimum required:
 - (d) steering axle load;
 - (e) driving/traction axle load.

Each constraint generates a boundary curve that expresses the maximum permissible payload of a vehicle as a function of the longitudinal position of its centre of gravity x [m], measured from the back of the cargo container, namely the side closer to the vehicle cabin. The intersection of the areas limited by the boundary curves, produces the LDD. Figure 3 illustrates the boundary curves generated by each constraint.

Figure 3: Determining the LDD by merging the boundary curves.

The calculation of the individual boundary curves of the load distribution plan will be now explained:

- a) The boundary curve (a) is determined by the maximum permissible front axle load, FT_{max} [tnf]. Using the equation of moments about the rear axle, the maximum weight is given by (2).

$$P_x \cdot (TWB - D - x) + U \cdot (TWB - Hu) - TWB \cdot FT_{max} = 0$$

$$P_x = \frac{TWB \cdot FT_{max} - U \cdot (TWB - Hu)}{TWB - D - x} \quad (2)$$

- b) The boundary curve (b) is determined by the maximum permissible rear axle load, RT_{max} [tnf]. Using the equation of moments about the front axle, the maximum weight is given by (3).

$$P_x \cdot (D + x) + U \cdot Hu - TWB \cdot RT_{max} = 0$$

$$P_x = \frac{TWB \cdot RT_{max} - U \cdot Hu}{D + x} \quad (3)$$

- c) The boundary curve (c) connecting the curved regions (a) and (b) stands for the maximum payload of the vehicle, P_{max} [tnf].

$$P_x = P_{max} \quad (4)$$

- d) The boundary curve (d) is determined by the minimum steering axle load, S_{min} [%]. Using the equation of moments about the rear axle, the maximum weight is given by (5).

$$S_{min} \cdot (P_x + U) \cdot TWB - U \cdot (TWB - Hu) + P_x \cdot (x + D - TWB) = 0$$

$$P_x = \frac{U \cdot (TWB - Hu - S_{min} \cdot TWB)}{S_{min} \cdot TWB + x + D - TWB} \quad (5)$$

- e) The boundary curve (e) is determined by the minimum driving axle load, T_{min} [%]. Using the equation of moments about the front axle, the maximum weight is given by (6).

$$-T_{min} \cdot (P_x + U) \cdot TWB + U \cdot Hu + P_x \cdot (x + D) = 0$$

$$P_x = \frac{U \cdot (T_{min} \cdot TWB - Hu)}{x + D - T_{min} \cdot TWB} \quad (6)$$

4.2. Transversal load distribution diagrams

The transversal position of the cargo CG is evaluated relatively to the vertical symmetry plane of the vehicle. The lateral offset of the centre of gravity of the cargo may have a significant impact on the carrying vehicle roll stability and result in unsafe driving conditions. It is required that the cargo should be evenly distributed. The lateral offset should typically not exceed a given percentage of the truck track width, but this value varies with the mechanical characteristics of the vehicle, such as the permissible tire pressure or the suspension spring deflection, as well as with the weight of the cargo. The load transfer ratio (*LTR*) quantifies the load transfer from one side of the vehicle to the other (El-Gindy, 1992). Using the side supporting loads S_L (left) and S_R (right) the *LTR* is calculated using (7).

$$LTR = \frac{S_L - S_R}{P + U} \quad (7)$$

This value varies between -1 and 1, being equal to zero when the load is evenly distributed, and taking the value 1 or -1 should the load be entirely transferred to one of the sides. The

mechanical characteristics of the vehicle impose a maximum value for the load transfer ratio (LTR_{Max}), which should be provided by the manufacturer of the vehicle. Using the theoretical track width of the vehicle (T), the container width (W), the location of the CG of the loaded vehicle (unladen vehicle weight + cargo load) measured from the back-bottom-left corner of the container, the calculation of the individual curve of the transverse load distribution plan is given by (8). Figure 4 presents a freebody diagram of a truck and its transversal LDD.

$$\frac{LTR_{Max} + 1}{2} \cdot (P_y + U) \cdot T - U \cdot \frac{T}{2} - P_y \cdot \left(\frac{T}{2} + \frac{W}{2} - y\right) = 0$$

$$P_y = \frac{-U \cdot T \cdot LTR_{Max}}{LTR_{Max} \cdot T - W + 2 \cdot y} \quad (8)$$

Figure 4: Transverse section of a truck.

5. Container loading algorithm with static stability and load balance

5.1. General algorithm architecture

The proposed container loading algorithm (CLA-SS-B) is an extension of the multi-population biased random-key genetic algorithm (BRKGA) with static stability proposed by Ramos *et al.* (2016a). For self containment purposes the basics of the original algorithm will be presented in the following sections. The innovative components of the algorithm are the solution fitness function that used the LDD of the vehicle, and the hard constraint extension to load balance. The CLA-SS-B algorithm, illustrated in Figure 5, has three main modules: a BRKGA problem-independent module, a BRKGA problem-specific module and

the hard constraint module. The first is responsible for the evolution of coded solutions (chromosomes), the second for decoding the chromosome, generating a solution and evaluating its fitness and the latter for enforcing the load balancing constraint.

Figure 5: CLA-SS-B framework

5.2. BRKGA evolutionary process

The problem independent module of the BRKGA is responsible for the evolutionary process of the populations over a number of generations (iterations). Each population is composed of a set of individuals (chromosomes), each composed by a number of genes (random-keys) with values generated independently in the real interval $[0, 1]$. The evolution is accomplished by the generation of new populations. The evolutionary process starts by ordering each population of individuals by non increasing order of the value of their fitness function. Each current population is then divided in two subsets: the elite individuals, those with the best values of the fitness function, and the non-elite ones, i.e. the remaining of the population. The new population is then formed by three subsets: the first is the elite population of the previous generation, the second is obtained by a reproduction process with one parent originating from the elite individuals and the other from the entire population

and the third subset is composed by mutant individuals. The offspring of the reproduction process is obtained using the parametrised uniform crossover (Spears & De Jong, 1991) where each gene of an offspring individual is determined by a given probability of the gene being inherited from the elite parent. After a predetermined number of generations the populations exchange between them a small number of individuals with the best fitness function values. The BRKGA can be explored in further detail in the paper of Gonçalves & Resende (2011).

5.3. Chromosome encoding and decoding

In the proposed CLA-SS-B algorithm the chromosome is an indirect representation of the solution, that is, additional procedures are required to obtain a solution from the chromosome. This approach is preferable to the direct representation of the solution, where the chromosomes represent the box placement coordinates, thus making both the overlap constraints harder to enforce and the feasibility of the offsprings that result from chromosome crossover harder to guarantee (Gonçalves & Resende, 2011). The adopted representation of the solution has two sets of genes. The first one is used to determine the box type placement sequence, that is, the sequence in which the box types are to be placed into the container. The second stands for one of the three orthogonal planes of the container, namely the plane upon which the layer for that specific type of box is to be built, hereafter called the filling plane.

Let chromosome $G = \{gene_1, gene_2, \dots, gene_g\}$ be an indirect representation of a CLP solution and let $M = \sum_{k=1}^K n_k$ represent the number of boxes to be loaded, K standing for the number of different box types, and n_k for the number of boxes of type k to pack in the container. The number of genes, g , of the chromosome is equal to $2M$. For the first M genes, each $gene_j$ represents the box type of the j^{th} box to be loaded, while the last M genes ($gene_{M+j}$) represent the layer filling plane of the j^{th} box to load. The layer filling plane of box j is determined using (9).

$$\begin{cases} 0 \leq gene_{M+j} < 1/3 & x - y \text{ plane} \\ 1/3 \leq gene_{M+j} < 2/3 & x - z \text{ plane} \\ 2/3 \leq gene_{M+j} < 1 & y - z \text{ plane} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

By sorting the first M genes in ascending order, a box type packing sequence is generated as well as the corresponding box filling plane.

5.4. Placement procedure

The placement procedure is a constructive heuristic that iteratively selects a box type, a box arrangement strategy and, using a spatial representation, a location for the box inside the container, until no more locations or boxes are available. According to the classification for placement procedures proposed by Ramos *et al.* (2016b), the CLA-SS-B adopts — as a box arrangement strategy — two dimensional arrangements of identical boxes, i.e., boxes grouped along two axes, generating layers, and for spatial representation, it resorts to the maximal-spaces concept, i.e., empty space described as a set of non-disjoint spaces,

corresponding to the largest parallelepiped shapes that can be defined in that empty space (Lai & Chan, 1997).

Let C be a container of depth (D), width (W) and height (H) carried by vehicle L and let $B = (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_K)$ be a set of box types, in which each box type $k = (1, \dots, K)$ is defined by its length (d_k), width (w_k), height (h_k), quantity (q_k) and weight (p_k). The placement procedure consists in an iterative process with the following four main steps:

- Step 1: Selection of a box type
- Step 2: Selection a *maximal-space*
- Step 3: Filling of the *maximal-space*
- Step 4: Update of the system information

Step 0: Initialization

$S = \{C\}$, set of *maximal-spaces*

$B = \{b_1, b_2, \dots, b_K\}$, set of box types to be packed into the container

$q_k = n_k$, number of boxes of type k to be packed into the container

$L = \emptyset$, set of boxes already loaded

P , Payload of loaded cargo

Step 1: Select the box type

In this step the type of box to be loaded is selected. To select the box type, the order obtained by the decoding procedure is followed. The i^{th} box type to consider for loading (let us denote it by b_k) is given by the box type that is in the i^{th} position of the packing sequence. If $q_k > 0$ the box type is selected, otherwise the next box type in the sequence is considered for loading.

Step 2: Selecting the maximal-space

In this step the *maximal-space* where the selected box type b_k is to be placed is selected. Let a *maximal-space* s be represented by its minimum and maximum coordinates, (x_{1s}, y_{1s}, z_{1s}) and (x_{2s}, y_{2s}, z_{2s}) , respectively, and by an Insertion Vertex V , with coordinates x_{1s}, y_{Vs}, z_{1s} , where $y_{Vs} = \min\{y_{s1}, (W - y_{s2})\}$. The *maximal-space* is selected in accordance with the back-bottom rule, namely the *maximal-space(s)* s with the smallest x_{1s} are first selected from S , then among these the one(s) with the smallest z_{1s} are chosen and finally the space(s) with the smallest y_{Vs} are singled out. Ties are broken by comparing the volume of the *maximal-spaces* and adopting the smallest one. Please notice that, the *maximal-spaces* being a non-disjoint set of spaces, two or more spaces may have vertices with the same coordinates, for which reason a tie-breaking rule is needed.

Step 3: Fill the maximal-space

To fill the *maximal-space*, a layer of identical boxes arranged in rows and columns is build. It should be noted that a box can be loaded in up to 6 different orientations — depending on the number of rotations allowed — and that each box orientation can have up

to two layer configurations, as determined by the i^{th} layer plane position obtained with the decoding procedure, which results in a total of 12 different possible configurations.

To fill the *maximal-space*, each box needs to observe a static stability filling condition, based on the static mechanical equilibrium conditions applied to rigid bodies that derive from Newton’s first and third laws of motion, as well as a maximum weight condition. The first condition considers that a box b can be loaded at (x, y, z) , if the projection of its geometric centre cg , of coordinates (x_{cg}, y_{cg}, z_{cg}) on plane $(0, 0, z)$, lies inside the support polygon SP of box b . The support polygon SP of box b is formed by the convex hull of all horizontal contact points of box b . A more detailed description of the static stability filling condition is presented in Ramos *et al.* (2016a). The second condition imposes that a box can be loaded only if the maximum payload of the vehicle is not exceeded with the placement of the box.

The layer configurations obtained are evaluated using the *best-overhanging* criterion. Firstly the layer fit is assessed by calculating the maximal gap between the vertical faces and the support polygon of the layer along the x - and y -axes. These fitness values are then ordered in non-decreasing order and finally the best layer is chosen considering a lexicographic order. Ties are broken first by the smallest gap along the z -axis between the layer and the *maximal-space* and secondly by the greatest number of boxes to be placed.

Step 4: Update the system information

At the end of each iteration of the placement procedure, if a layer of m boxes of type k was loaded, the number of boxes yet to be packed q_k and the payload of the packed cargo P are updated, and the occupied *maximal-space* s is removed from the respective list S of *maximal-spaces*, which is then updated using the “Interval Generation” procedure proposed by Lai & Chan (1997).

The placement procedure is repeated until all boxes are packed, the last position of the packing sequence is reached or no more *maximal-spaces* are available.

5.5. Compute the solution fitness

The computation of the fitness of each solution is a procedure that takes three factors into consideration: the container volume used, the static stability of the cargo arrangement and the balance of the loaded vehicle.

The procedure first determines the statically stable set of boxes T using the physical packing sequence algorithm (PPSA), which incorporates static stability as presented in Ramos *et al.* (2016a). Even though static stability conditions have been assessed during the placement procedure, these are not sufficient to guarantee static stability, as they perform only a local check of static stability when the *maximal-spaces* are filled, whereas the PPSA globally checks and imposes static stability after the entire loading arrangement is completed. Upon determining the boxes that can be loaded with static stability, the CG along the x and y -axis of the cargo arrangement T is determined by (10) and (11).

$$CG_x = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T p_t \times \frac{x_{1t} + x_{2t}}{2}}{\sum_{t=1}^T p_t} \quad (10)$$

$$CG_y = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T p_t \times \frac{y_{1t} + y_{2t}}{2}}{\sum_{t=1}^T p_t} \quad (11)$$

After determining the CG_x and CG_y of the cargo arrangement, the maximum admissible payload P_x and P_y for that location is determined using the LDD's of the transportation vehicle. The value of ΔP is determined by (12).

$$\Delta P = \begin{cases} P - P_x & \text{if } P > P_x \\ P - P_y & \text{if } P < P_x \text{ and } P > P_y \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The solution fitness function is determined by (13), where N_k is the number of loaded boxes of type k in T and SF is the shipping factor used to determine the volumetric weight of the cargo. The volumetric weight (VW) is an estimate of the cargo's weight based on its volume V ($VW = V \times SF$), and is used as a pricing technique for commercial freight transport to properly charge bulky but light items. In practice, the shipping costs are calculated based on a weight that is the maximum between the actual weight and the volumetric weight. Each means of transportation has its own shipping factor and generally the following applies:

- Sea transport — $SF = 1000 \text{ kg/m}^3$
- Truck transport — $SF = 333 \text{ kg/m}^3$
- Air transport — $SF = 167 \text{ kg/m}^3$

The use of the shipping factor in the solution fitness, in the term $(\Delta P/SF)$, serves to guide the BRKGA to provide a load balanced arrangement of the payload packed in a container.

$$\%Vol = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K N_k \times (d_k \times w_k \times h_k) - \frac{\Delta P}{SF}}{D \times W \times H} \times 100\% \quad (13)$$

5.6. Load balance hard constraint enforcement

As the load balance is only taken into account in the solution fitness evaluation, and is not treated as a hard constraint, it may happen that the final solution provided by the BRKGA phase of the algorithm is not load balanced. Therefore, when these situations occur, the penalty in the fitness function, $\Delta P/SF$, is multiplied by 10 and an extra 50 generations are run. This procedure is repeated until a load balanced cargo arrangement is achieved.

6. Experimental results

This section is dedicated to the experimental evaluation of the performance of the proposed algorithm. Extensive computational experiments have been conducted on a new set of test problems.

6.1. New problem generator

In Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995) a test problem generator was proposed for the single container loading problem. The procedure ensures that the total cargo volume will not exceed a predetermined target value and will be as close as possible to this value in the sense that the major difference will be the volume of the largest box. Standard test cases were generated by adopting the dimensions of a 20ft ISO container ($L = 587, W = 233$ and $H = 220$) for the carrying container, and integer numbers randomly selected from the intervals $[30, 120]$, $[25, 100]$ and $[20, 80]$ for the box dimensions. In the literature on CLP the test problems resulting from this problem generator are known as the BR test instances. The majority of computational experiments performed with algorithms for the container loading problem with load balance constraint adopt the BR test problems. However, the problem generator proposed by Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995) did not take the weight of the boxes into consideration. To overcome this drawback different authors have generated the box weight, as can be observed in table 2, adopting however different ranges for the uniform distribution. In some cases the reproducibility of the test problems was even compromised, since information concerning their generation is missing, thus hampering comparisons between algorithms.

In order to compute the performance of the algorithms proposed here, we contrived an extension of the test problem generator presented by Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995), which includes item weight generation and guarantees the reproducibility of the test problems. The generator was coded in C++ and compiled with Microsoft Visual Studio 2012. An executable version compiled for Windows, its source code, as well as the test problems have been made available at <http://www.fe.up.pt/~esicup/>.

After the generation of the box dimensions, their vertical orientation and demand, as proposed by Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995), the weight is generated as described below. It should be noted that, even though the uniform distribution is — owing to its simplicity — usually used in the literature for the generation of the box weight, we adopt the beta distribution function, where $f(x, \alpha, \beta)$ is the probability density function of the beta distribution with parameters α and β . The density of the container (D_c) is used as the mean value of the beta distribution ($E[x]$), and 50% of this value is defined as the minimum value of the range.

The maximum value of the range is then calculated accordingly. The density of the boxes is generated using the inverse transform sampling technique for generating random numbers following the beta distribution, and the pseudo-random generator for generating random numbers following the uniform distribution already used by Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995). The weight of each box is then obtained by multiplying the generated density by the volume of the corresponding box, the procedure being repeated for each box. The pseudo-code for the complete algorithm for the problem generator is presented in algorithm Appendix A.

The main advantage offered by the beta distribution function is its versatility, as it assumes a variety of different shapes depending on the values of its α and β parameters. The use of this distribution for generating test problems in cutting and packing problems was proposed by Silva *et al.* (2014).

In this work, we consider three different combinations of α and β parameters for the beta distribution, namely $f(x, 2, 2)$, $f(x, 5, 2)$ and $f(x, 2, 5)$. All three distributions have as mean value the density of the container, but different amplitudes are obtained depending on the α and β parameters, as can be observed in figure 6.

Figure 6: Beta distribution.

In addition to the weight of the boxes, the characteristics of the vehicle are also required to evaluate the load balance. For the calculation of the LDD the data of the vehicle, as defined in Section 4, are needed. Since it was intended to use the BR instances, the decision of selecting the vehicle took into account the dimensions of the container used in the BR instances ($L = 587$, $W = 233$ and $H = 220$). Thus, the vehicle parameters were selected based on the characteristics of the “FE Eu6 6x2 Rigid Air Ride” truck of Volvo Trucks (n.d), are presented in Table 3.

6.2. Design of the computational experiments

The computational experiments were divided into two stages.

In the first stage we propose to demonstrate that load balanced solutions are not obtained *a priori* by the CLP algorithms. The solutions obtained by the Maximal Space Algorithm proposed by Parreño *et al.* (2008), the Biased Random Key Genetic Algorithm proposed by Gonçalves & Resende (2012) and the multi-population biased random-key genetic algorithm

Table 3: Vehicle parameters.

Parameters	Values	[mm]	Parameters	Values
U		6840	P_{max}	19.160 kgf
RU		2800	RT_{max}	19.000 kgf
D		832	FT_{max}	7.100 kgf
TWB		4397	T_{min}	25 %
T		1831	S_{min}	25 %
			LTR_{max}	10 %

(CLA-SS) with static stability proposed by Ramos *et al.* (2016b) are evaluated considering the longitudinal and transversal position of the CG of the cargo on the LDD. If the CG of the cargo is positioned outside the feasible domain defined by the LDD, the solution is considered unbalanced. Thus, the metric used for the evaluation of the algorithms is the number of unbalanced solutions, since load balance should be considered as a hard constraint.

BR1 to BR15 problem instances are organized into 15 classes, with a total of 100 instances per class. The heterogeneity of the boxes increases from just 3 different box types (in BR1) to 100 box types in BR15. The average number of boxes per box type also varies from 50.15 boxes per type in BR1 to 1.33 in BR15. Three different combinations of α and β parameters for the beta distribution ($f(x, 2, 2)$, $f(x, 5, 2)$ and $f(x, 2, 5)$) are used for the generation of weights for the boxes, since a biased generation of these values is undesirable.

It is proposed in this work the CLA-SS-B algorithm which ensures load balanced and stable solutions, while retaining a good performance in what concerns volume occupation. The second stage of the computational experiments is dedicated to the evaluation of this algorithm. For that purpose, two different strategies are considered in what regards static stability: (1) full base support and (2) static mechanical equilibrium with the weight of the items generated with the $f(x, 2, 5)$ beta distribution.

6.3. Evaluation of load balance on existing literature solutions

This subsection is dedicated to the analysis of the load balance on solutions obtained by the algorithms proposed by Parreño *et al.* (2008), Gonçalves & Resende (2013) and Ramos *et al.* (2016a). Table 4 presents, for the different algorithms, the container volume used (in percentage of the total container volume) and the number of unbalanced solutions for each class of instances and combination of α and β distribution parameters. In the last lines of the table the average values of the volume occupation achieved and the total number of unbalanced solutions obtained are presented.

The worst case, in terms of number of unbalanced solutions was obtained with the CLA-SS algorithm with the weight of the items generated with the $f(x, 2, 5)$ beta distribution, where almost 32% of the 1500 CLP solutions were unbalanced. Still in terms of unbalanced solutions, the best combination of the CLP algorithm and beta distribution for item weight generation was obtained by Parreño *et al.* (2008) with $f(x, 5, 2)$, with only 5,5% of unbalanced solutions out of the 1500. These results confirm that load balance does not happen by chance and this constraint is not fully guaranteed in any approach published in the literature, being so far considered just as a soft constraint.

Table 4: Full Base Support variant

Problem classes	Parreño <i>et al.</i> (2008)				Gonçalves & Resende (2012)				Ramos <i>et al.</i> (2016a)			
	% Vol	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 5$	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 2$	$\alpha = 5$ $\beta = 2$	% Vol	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 5$	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 2$	$\alpha = 5$ $\beta = 2$	% Vol	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 5$	$\alpha = 2$ $\beta = 2$	$\alpha = 5$ $\beta = 2$
BR 1	80.77	44	43	28	94.34	46	46	33	93.86	45	45	29
BR 2	79.77	35	28	17	94.88	42	42	28	94.55	47	42	22
BR 3	81.07	26	17	9	95.05	51	52	24	94.75	55	53	26
BR 4	79.76	29	15	5	94.75	49	47	16	94.63	40	41	18
BR 5	80.01	24	16	6	94.58	45	40	15	94.38	41	34	13
BR 6	79.17	25	20	6	94.39	47	43	13	94.24	48	40	14
BR 7	76.72	14	11	6	93.74	31	29	9	93.82	31	25	10
BR 8	75.30	17	7	2	92.65	31	25	3	93.16	32	27	1
BR 9	74.80	10	7	3	91.90	28	20	0	92.62	34	21	0
BR 10	73.40	9	7	0	91.28	17	10	2	92.09	22	13	1
BR 11	72.80	1	0	0	90.39	12	6	0	91.56	24	10	0
BR 12	71.27	1	1	0	89.81	20	16	1	91.28	13	7	1
BR 13	70.48	1	1	0	89.27	16	4	1	90.93	14	8	1
BR 14	69.01	2	2	1	88.57	10	6	0	90.38	16	3	0
BR 15	69.52	2	1	0	87.96	8	5	0	90.08	7	0	0
(BR 1-7)	79.61	197	150	77	94.53	311	299	138	94.32	307	280	132
(BR 8-15)	72.07	43	26	6	90.23	142	92	7	91.51	162	89	4
(BR 1-15)	75.59	240	176	83	92.24	453	391	145	92.82	469	369	136

Analysing the results, it is clear that the algorithm proposed by Parreño *et al.* (2008) presents the smallest number of unbalanced solutions, which is intrinsically related to the fact that it is the algorithm exhibiting the lowest percentages of container occupation, and therefore a lower cargo weight, providing a wider range for the location of the centre of gravity of the cargo.

The test problems with the weight of the boxes generated using beta function $f(x, 2, 5)$ have proved to be the most challenging ones, since regardless of the algorithm this combination of α and β parameters displays the highest number of unbalanced solutions. Hence, the additional computational experiments to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm will only consider this set of parameters.

It is also worthy of note that the number of unbalanced solutions decreases with the increase in the heterogeneity of the class instances.

6.4. BRKGA parameters

The genetic algorithm parameters used in the CLA-SS-B algorithm are based on the recommended parameter value settings proposed by Gonçalves & Resende (2011) for a generic BRKGA, on the parameters used by Gonçalves & Resende (2012) and Gonçalves & Resende (2013) for the specific BRKGA developed for the CLP, and finally on those used by Ramos *et al.* (2016a) for the BRKGA developed for the CLP with static stability. The parameters are presented in Table 5.

During the preliminary tests more than two populations were used, and we concluded then that the improvements in the solutions obtained with a higher number of populations did not compensate for the significant increase in the running times, and that the adoption of two populations led to the best balance time/quality. In the preliminary tests the first 10 problem instances of each of the 15 classes were used. The results of the average percentage

Table 5: Genetic algorithm parameters used in all computational experiments.

Parameters	Values
Top	15%
Bottom	15%
Crossover probability	0.7
Population size	$20 \times$ number of boxes
Number of populations	2
Exchange between pop.	Every 15 generations
Stopping criteria	after 1000 generations

of container volume usage and the average CPU times as a function of the number of populations are presented in Figure 7. As can be observed there is an increase from 1 to 2 populations, and a small gap between the results obtained for 2, 3 and 4 populations. Considering that the processing time is proportional to the number of populations, the number of populations was set to 2.

Figure 7: Influence of the # of populations in the average volume usage

6.5. Analysis of the CLA-SS-B solutions

This section is dedicated to the analysis of the computational results obtained by the four versions of the CLA-SS-B heuristic mentioned at the end of subsection 6.2. Regarding stability, two different strategies were used: the full base support constraint and the static mechanical equilibrium conditions.

The results obtained are presented in table 6. The columns of the table are firstly organised according to the strategy used to guarantee static stability: full base support or static mechanical equilibrium. The second level of organisation is related to load balance, with a first column presenting results without any load balance consideration and the second

column displaying the results obtained when load balance is integrated in the fitness function. As mentioned in section 5.6, this strategy does not absolutely ensure that a load balanced solution is obtained in the end of the predetermined number of generations, requiring the change of the fitness function and an increase in the number of generations, until a balanced solution is achieved.

Columns “%Vol”, “#Unb.” and “Time (s)” display the average percentage of container volume usage, the number of unbalanced solutions obtained, and the average CPU time. Column “%Vol (Total)” presents the average percentage of container volume considering all the generations. Column “#Unb.(1000)” presents the number of unbalanced solutions obtained after 1000 generations.

Column “%Vol Trade-off”, presents the trade-off in volume occupation when using the CLA-SS-B algorithm considering load balance on the fitness function. The results show that considering load balance on the fitness function had a low impact on the volume utilization, since it produced an average difference not exceeding -0.68 percentage points in the Full Support Variant and -0.79 in the Static Mechanical Equilibrium variant. The proposed strategy proved to be very effective, since in the total of 1500 test problems only 10 required extending the number of generations in the Full Support Variant and 7 in the Static Mechanical Equilibrium variant.

In the light of the solutions obtained imposing only stability constraint, we realise that static mechanical equilibrium leads to a higher volume occupation than that obtained with full base support, which also justifies a higher number of unbalanced solutions in the version with static mechanical equilibrium when load balance wasn’t considered. The fitness function including volume occupation, load balance and static mechanical equilibrium proved to be very effective, since only 7 solutions were classified as unbalanced after 1000 generations (all became balanced after extending a maximum of 50 generations), and the average volume occupation was 93.13%, whereas the solutions generated without load balance produced 521 unbalanced solutions, and an average volume occupation of 93.93%.

Table 6: Experiments results ($\alpha = 2, \beta = 5$)

Problem Classes	Full Support							Static Mechanical Equilibrium							
	Without Balance			With Balance				% Vol Trade-off	Without Balance			With Balance			
	% Vol	#Unb.	% Time (s)	% Vol Total	#Unb. (1000)	% Time (s)	% Vol		#Unb.	% Time (s)	% Vol Total	#Unb. (1000)	% Time (s)	% Vol Trade-off	
BR 1	93.86	46	39	91.31	2	60	-2.55	94.77	43	522	91.94	1	504	-2.83	
BR 2	94.55	48	37	92.40	2	56	-2.15	95.39	45	545	93.02	0	549	-2.37	
BR 3	94.75	55	39	93.32	2	57	-1.43	95.52	54	665	93.97	0	660	-1.55	
BR 4	94.63	40	40	93.58	1	57	-1.06	95.48	53	600	94.35	0	585	-1.13	
BR 5	94.38	43	42	93.60	2	59	-0.78	95.38	44	615	94.51	0	635	-0.86	
BR 6	94.24	48	44	93.48	1	61	-0.76	95.37	51	651	94.42	0	644	-0.94	
BR 7	93.82	31	49	93.35	0	65	-0.48	95.14	39	685	94.56	1	684	-0.58	
BR 8	93.16	32	58	92.92	0	73	-0.24	94.72	43	791	94.43	1	785	-0.29	
BR 9	92.62	34	64	92.45	0	77	-0.16	94.50	28	800	94.24	2	803	-0.25	
BR 10	92.09	22	72	92.01	0	85	-0.08	93.99	26	873	93.69	1	878	-0.30	
BR 11	91.56	24	77	91.47	0	90	-0.09	93.49	28	913	93.37	1	907	-0.12	
BR 12	91.28	13	83	91.06	0	96	-0.22	92.77	26	960	92.64	0	961	-0.13	
BR 13	90.93	14	88	90.77	0	102	-0.16	91.66	19	1021	91.40	0	1015	-0.27	
BR 14	90.38	16	94	90.37	0	108	-0.01	90.97	18	1054	90.46	0	1057	-0.51	
BR 15	90.08	7	101	89.97	0	114	-0.10	89.74	4	1096	89.97	0	1089	0.23	
Mean (BR 1-7)	94.32	311	41	93.01	10	59	-1.31	95.29	329	612	93.83	2	609	-1.47	
Mean (BR 8-15)	91.51	162	79	91.38	0	93	-0.13	92.73	192	938	92.52	5	937	-0.21	
Mean (BR 1-15)	92.82	473	62	92.14	10	77	-0.68	93.93	521	786	93.13	7	784	-0.79	

7. Conclusions and further research

In this paper we have addressed three of the most important practical relevant constraints for the CLP, regarding safety on road transport: stability, weight limit and load balance. We present an hybrid genetic algorithm based on a multi-population biased random key genetic algorithm and an extension to the problem generator of Bischoff & Ratcliff (1995). An innovative procedure for load balance evaluation is presented, in alternative to the minimization of the distance between the cargo CG and the geometric centre of the container: a feasibility domain for the cargo CG defined by LDDs that takes the real characteristics of the transport vehicle into account.

The computational experiments have shown that the algorithms for the container loading problem so far published in the literature do not naturally generate load balanced solutions, even when cargo stability is taken into consideration. This is only to be expected since cargo stability and load balance are different constraints and acting upon cargo stability does not guarantee load balance, which strongly relates to the location of centre of gravity of the cargo. From the results obtained with the experiments with the two versions of the new algorithm that incorporate weight balance goals — with stability guaranteed by full base support and by the mechanical equilibrium conditions — it can be concluded that it is very effective. Finally, it is demonstrated that it is possible to consider simultaneously static stability, weight and load balance as distinct constraints without compromising the volume usage of the container.

Future research on this problem will certainly consider its integration with the vehicle routing problem, i.e. how to build solutions that remain balanced even when the cargo is partially unloaded at the various destinations. The integration of the vehicle routing problem with the container loading problem has already been studied, and important papers on this topic are available in the literature, but cargo balance was only sporadically considered and this constraint has an important impact on the applicability of automatically generated solutions. In this context of cargo balance in multi-drop scenarios, guaranteeing balance by just removing boxes ceases to be feasible, and box displacement will have to be incorporated into the overall solution approach. Even though a meta-heuristic has been used in this paper, there is clearly room for mathematical programming based approaches.

Acknowledgements

The second author was supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology) within the grant SFRH/BPD/98981/2013. The research was partially supported by ERDF European Regional Development Fund through the Operational Programme for Competitiveness and Internationalisation - COMPETE 2020 Programme within project “POCI-01-0145-FEDER-006961 ”, and by National Funds through the Portuguese funding agency, FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia as part of project “UID/EEA/50014/2013”.

The authors are very grateful to Jaime Lebre for the remarkable work done in the final revision of this paper, that went far beyond the improvement of English usage.

Appendix A. Problem generator

Algorithm 1: Problem generator

Input: Let Sd be the current seed, let m be the number of test problems, T_c be the cargo target volume, L, W, H be the length, width and height of the container respectively, n be the number of different box types, $a_j, b_j, j = 1, \dots, 3$ be the lower and upper limits on box dimensions respectively, L be the box stability limit, P_{max} be the maximum payload of the transport vehicle and $f(x, \alpha, \beta)$ be the probability density function of the beta distribution with α and β shape parameters

Output: Set of m test problems

```

randomGen ( $\alpha, \beta, Min, Max$ )
  | randomly generates an integer number in the interval  $[Min, Max]$  according to  $f(x, \alpha, \beta)$ 
  | return integer number;
pseudo-randomGen ( $Sd$ )
  | variant of the multiplicative congruential method attributed to Lehmer (Hutchinson, 1966)
  | return integer number;
begin
  for  $t=1$  to  $m$  do
    for  $i=1$  to  $10$  do
      |  $r \leftarrow$  pseudo-randomGen( $Sd$ )                                 $\triangleright$  Discard the first ten random numbers
    end for
    for  $i=1$  to  $n$  do
      for  $j=1$  to  $3$  do
        |  $r_j \leftarrow$  pseudo-randomGen( $Sd$ )
        |  $d_{ij} \leftarrow a_j + \lfloor r_j \cdot (b_j - a_j + 1) \rfloor$            $\triangleright$  Determine box dimensions
      end for
      for  $j=1$  to  $3$  do
        |  $\triangleright$  Determine vertical orientation for each box dimension
        | if  $((d_{ij}/Min\{d_{i1}, d_{i2}, d_{i3}\}) < L)$  then  $vo_{ij} \leftarrow 1$ 
        | else  $vo_{ij} \leftarrow 0$ 
      end for
      Sort  $d_{ij}$  by decreasing order
       $l_i \leftarrow d_{i1}$ 
       $w_i \leftarrow d_{i2}$ 
       $h_i \leftarrow d_{i3}$ 
       $q_i \leftarrow 1$ 
       $v_i \leftarrow l_i \cdot w_i \cdot h_i$ 
    end for
     $C \leftarrow \sum_{i=1}^n q_i \cdot v_i$ 
     $r \leftarrow$  pseudo-randomGen( $Sd$ )
     $k \leftarrow 1 + \lfloor r \cdot n \rfloor$ 
    while  $(T_c < C + v_k)$  do
      |  $q_k \leftarrow q_k + 1$ 
      |  $C \leftarrow \sum_{i=1}^n q_i \cdot v_i$ 
      |  $r \leftarrow$  pseudo-randomGen( $Sd$ )
      |  $k \leftarrow 1 + \lfloor r \cdot n \rfloor$ 
       $\triangleright$  Determine box quantity
    end while
     $D_c \leftarrow P_{max}/T_c$ 
     $D_c^{min} \leftarrow 0.5 \cdot D_c$ 
     $D_c^{max} \leftarrow (D_c - D_c^{min})/E[x] + D_c^{min}$ 
     $\triangleright E[x]$  expected value of  $f(x, \alpha, \beta)$ 
    for  $i=1$  to  $n$  do
      |  $r \leftarrow$  randomGen( $\alpha, \beta, D_c^{min}, D_c^{max}$ )
      |  $w_i \leftarrow r \cdot v_i$ 
       $\triangleright$  Determine box weight
    end for
  end for
end

```

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